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TENTATIVE OPTICS OF THE COLLIDER RING AND PULSED SYNCHROTRONS

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Abstract:

This report gives the structure of the repository where the optics files for the pulsed synchrotrons and colliders are located.

MuCol Consortium, 2024

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Executive summary

This document explains the structure of the folder containing the optics files for the pulsed synchrotrons and collider. This document gives also some preliminary optics results.

1. INTRODUCTION

This document explains the structure of the optics files for the collider at 10 TeV center of mass and chain of the pulsed synchrotrons as defined in the green field scenario (see Table 1 and

Table 2).

The repository of the optics files can be downloaded here: <https://gitlab.cern.ch/muon-collider-bd/rcs-optics.git>. This repository contains lattices for the RCS and the collider, along with example notebooks. The code for creating lattices, performing ramping in the RCS, and conducting tracking simulations will be added in the future. The structure of the repository is the following:

- *Lattice*. Contains the lattice files for each RCS, organized into subfolders (rcs1 to rcs4). The lattices at injection and extraction energies are stored in JSON format to be loaded in Xsuite software [1] and also in MAD-X [2] sequence format (with the suffix .seq for the sequence and .madx for the MAD-X file). The lattice (version 0.6) of the collider is given in MAD-X format in the folder collider.
- *Examples*. Includes example Jupyter notebooks that demonstrate how to use the lattices.
- *Toolkit*. Will contain the core code for generating lattices, handling ramping, and performing tracking studies.

Table 1: Tentative parameter table for the acceleration chain.

Parameter	Unit	RCS1	RCS2	RCS3	RCS4
Hybrid RCS	-	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Repetition rate	Hz	5	5	5	5
Circumference	m	5990	5990	10700	35000
Injection energy	GeV	63	314	750	1500
Extraction energy	GeV	314	750	1500	5000
Energy ratio		5.0	2.4	2.0	3.3
Assumed survival rate		0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Acceleration time	ms	0.34	1.10	2.37	6.37
Revolution period	us	20	20	36	117
Number of turns		17	55	66	55
Required energy gain per turn	GeV	14.8	7.9	11.4	63.6
Average accel. gradient	MV/m	2.44	1.33	1.06	1.83
Number of bunches per species		1	1	1	1
Inj bunch population	10 ¹²	2.7	2.4	2.2	2
Ext bunch population	10 ¹²	2.4	2.2	2	1.8
Vert. norm. emittance	mm	25	25	25	25
Hor. norm. emittance	mm	25	25	25	25
Long. norm emittance	eVs	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
Total straight section length	m	2335	2335	3977	10367
Length with NC magnets	m	3655	2539	4366	20376
Length with SC magnets	m	-	1115	2358	4257
Max NC dipole field	T	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
Max SC dipole field	T	-	10	10	16
Ramp rate	T/s	4200	3282	1519	565
Main RF frequency	GHz	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3
Harmonic number		25900	25900	46300	151400
Total survival rate		0.9	0.81	0.729	0.6561
Packing Fraction	%	61	61	62.8	70.4
Beam current per bunch	mA	21.67	19.5	9.88	2.75
Beam power	kW	640	310	225	350
Number of Arcs		34	26	26	26
Relative path length difference	1.00E-06	0	8.29	1.96	1.71
Aperture NC magnets	mm	56.0	126.0	95.0	91.0
Aperture SC magnets	mm	-	80.0	75.0	62.0
Transition Gamma		40.8	29.6	37.1	59.2
Momentum compaction factor	1.00E-04	6.02	11.4	7.28	2.85

Table 2: Tentative parameter table for the collider.

Parameter	Unit	Target Value
Center of mass energy	TeV	10
Beam energy	TeV	5
Relativistic Lorentz factor		47322
Circumference	m	8668.8
Dist. of last magnet to IP	m	6
Repetition rate	Hz	5
Bunch intensity (one bunch per beam)		1.80E+12
Injected beam power per beam	MW	7.2
Normalized transverse rms emittance	um	25
Longitudinal norm. rms emittance	eVs	0.025
RMS bunch length in space	mm	1.5
RMS bunch length in time domain	ns	0.005
Twiss betatron function at the IP	mm	1.5
Transverse rms beam size at the IP	um	0.9
Tune shift due to beam-beam		~0.078
Maximum beta	km	~800
Energy loss per turn	MeV	27.2
RF voltage	MV	30

2. PULSED SYNCHROTRONS

The optics functions of the different lattices can be generated by using the jupyter notebook *plot_optics.ipynb* in the folder *examples* or by running the MAD-X files (suffix *.madx* in the folder *lattice/rcs[1-4]*) and by using a software like gnuplot to plot the optics function from the generated *tfs* file. An output example is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 for the lattice of the RCS1 to RCS4 at injection energy. Due to the superperiodicity of the synchrotron, only one arc is shown for each of them. Each cell begins and ends with one set of cavities. The length of the quadrupoles has been optimized to keep a pole field near 1 T. The chromaticity is corrected with two sextupole families in each arc.

Figure 1: Betatron functions (top) and dispersion function (below) in one arc of the RCS1 (left) and RCS2 (right) at injection energy.

Figure 2: Betatron functions (top) and dispersion function (below) in one arc of the RCS3 (left) and RCS4 (right) at injection energy.

3. COLLIDER

The optics functions in the collider ring and near the interaction point (IP) are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The optical functions are for the case of a betatron function of 1.5 mm at the IP in both planes. More details on the design of the collider optics can be found in [3].

Figure 3: Betatron functions and dispersion function in the collider ring.

Figure 4: Betatron functions and dispersion function near the interaction point in the collider ring.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Iadarola, R. De Maria, S. Łopaciuk, A. Abramov, X. Buffat, D. Demetriadou, L. Deniau, P. Hermes, P. Kicsiny, P. Kruyt, A. Latina, L. Mether, K. Paraschou, G. Sterbini, F. Van Der Veken, P. Belanger, P. Niedermayer, D. Di Croce and T. Pieloni, "Xsuite: An Integrated Beam Physics Simulation Framework," in *HB2023*, 2024.
- [2] "MAD-X Project website," [Online]. Available: <https://madx.web.cern.ch/>.
- [3] K. Skoufaris and C. Carli, "Update on collider optics design," IMCC and MuCol Annual Meeting - 13 March 2024.
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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
IP	Interaction point
RCS	Rapid Cycling Synchrotron
RMS	Root Mean Square